

developed cultivars from resistant donors like W.1257, W.1263, Ptb 18, Ptb 21, and Leuang 152 but have not achieved consistent resistance and yield.

In 3 years of wet-season trials, more than 70 varieties from various parts of India have been tested and a number have been found promising (see table).

The rice brown planthopper and its predator, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, on some rice cultivars in India

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In a varietal trial of 27 rice cultivars during kharif 1976, hopperburn was noted in November in mature grains. Examination revealed the presence of the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* Stal. and its predator, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter.

Both insects were found on all the cultivars and the predator was found invariably associated with the pest. The number of planthoppers varied from 5 to 133/sq m with a mean of 45 ± 6 ; that of the predator, from 37 to 423/sq m with

a mean of 187 ± 25 . The hopperburn was noted in only one of three replications with the variety IET 3229 indicating, as did observations in several farmers' fields, that the pest infestation was highly localized and that in the absence of natural enemies the insects would have caused much more crop damage.

The *Cyrtorhinus* population was about four times the planthopper's, and the population varied together ($r = + 0.88$).

The present data support the statement of Manjurath et al., who reported that until the crop flowered, the brown planthopper population generally exceeded that of the predator, but as the crop neared harvest, the situation reversed.

Cyrtorhinus seems a promising predator. We have developed methods for mass-rearing it in the laboratory, and for making inundative, timely releases in brown planthopper-infested fields to evaluate its value as a biological control agent.

List of scientists in brown planthopper research

E. A. Heinrichs, Entomology Department, International Rice Research Institute

At the brown planthopper symposium held at IRRI 18–22 April 1977, a preliminary list of scientists involved in research on the brown planthopper was developed. The list includes 103 names and addresses of scientists from 13 countries. Research areas listed are taxonomy; migration; surveillance and forecasting; biogeography; flight behavior; bionomics; varietal, breeding resistance; physiology; ecology; chemical, biological, cultural, and integrated control.

To obtain a copy of the list, write the Entomology Department, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines.

Populations of *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* on and yields of selected rice cultivar. Mandya, Karnataka, India, kharif 1976.

Cultivar	Yield (kg/plot) ^a	<i>N. lugens</i> (no./sq m)	<i>C. lividipennis</i> (no./sq m)
IET 1444	4.61	68	268
IET 2222	4.13	11	54
IET 2662	4.26	11	41
IET 2707	4.03	68	261
IET 2742	3.56	29	53
IET 2914	3.21	57	295
IET 2924	3.76	48	343
IET 2967	3.81	13	43
IET 3116	4.39	15	45
IET 3279	3.86	12	37
IET 3325	3.92	55	273
IET 3331	3.43	33	85
IET 3626	4.48	63	268
IET 3629	4.57	57	315
IET 3630	4.34	95	350
IET 4111	3.95	53	228
IET 4112	4.00	59	223
IET 4554	2.85	70	333
IET 4556	4.09	133	288
IET 5704	4.49	24	113
IET 5857	4.41	26	105
IET 5858	4.63	5	79
IET 5859	3.75	8	67
Ratna	4.26	101	372
Cauvery	4.30	90	423
IET 5860	4.20	15	43
MR 272	5.41	7	53
Mean	4.10	45	187
SE _m		6.5	24.9
F test	*	NS	NS
CD (0.05)	1.10		
CV (%)	16.2		

^aPlot size = 6.75 sq m.

*Significant at 5% level.

Brown planthopper predator, *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*.